

Dynamically Loaded Marine Composite Structures

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ABSTRACT

This paper discusses analysis and testing methods for marine composite panel structures subjected to dynamic pressure loads associated with slamming. Prediction methods for the magnitude and time history of slam induced pressure loads are described and compared to scantling code approaches, and a new technique for representing realistic time domain pressure distributions presented. The new method is used for applying slamming loads to transient dynamic finite element analysis of foam core sandwich panels. Predictions are compared to results of experimental testing in a novel Servo-hydraulic Slam Test System (SSTS). Traditional approaches to performing this type of test are based around the concept of drop testing, where a weighted panel is dropped a controlled vertical distance onto a water surface. The SSTS utilises a computer controlled servo-hydraulic system to enable full-scale hull sections to be impacted into a free surface of water with controlled velocity. By providing full control over motion of panel during impact the system can reproduce motions measured on real vessels. The results of this study demonstrate that the pressure simulation method proposed does accurately represent the pressure observed in slamming tests, and that transient dynamic finite element modelling can be used simulate composite panel responses to a slamming load.

KEYWORDS: dynamic, marine, slamming, sandwich panel, finite element analysis

INTRODUCTION

Although fibre reinforced polymer composite materials have been widely used in the marine industry for over 40 years current marine vessel design codes and regulations are still limited in their ability to address the behaviour of modern composite structures, particularly for dynamic load cases such as slamming. The usual design approach for marine sandwich panels is to treat them as flat plates with either simply supported or fixed edges. Static and impact pressure loads are generally taken as uniform across the panels with magnitudes given by empirical formulae. In reality many panels are not flat, and slamming pressures in particular are not uniformly distributed. Pressure pulses associated with slamming type events are typically of very short duration (5-50 ms), meaning that strain rates in the structure can be very high.

Some scantling authorities allow the use of so-called "direct calculation" methods, where engineering calculations using tools such as finite element analysis can be used to design the structure. Using these tools for a dynamic load case such as slamming poses significant challenges for the designer, particularly the definition of realistic load cases. This paper describes research work which focuses on analysis and testing methods for slam loaded composite panels, including:

- Predicting the magnitude and time history of slam induced pressure loads
- Transient dynamic finite element analysis (FEA) of sandwich panels subjected to slamming loads.
- Development of a unique servo-hydraulic controlled testing system for slam testing.
- Correlation of measured and predicted pressures and panel responses

This research is part of a programme of marine related activities at Industrial Research Limited, including modelling and full-scale measurement of vessel motions, loads and structural responses for displacement and planing craft [1]. Structural testing has included dynamic testing of skin materials and sandwich beams, and static pressure panel testing. These activities concentrate on the types of vessels that are relevant to the New Zealand marine industry, which are typically relatively small (6-50m) high performance power and sailing vessels including those shown in Figures 1 to 4.

Figure 1. 22m luxury yacht

Figure 2. 12m rigid hull inflatable police craft

Figure 3. 21m displacement catamaran

Figure 4. 14.5 m planing launch

PRESSURE PREDICTION METHODS

Efforts have been made since beginning of the 19th century to predict the dynamic loads on High Speed Craft (HSC). One of the first major works on the subject was that done by von Karman who studied slamming pressures on seaplane pontoons during landing [2]. von Karman's work formed the basis for many subsequent further developments, including those by Wagner [3]; Stavovy and Chuang [4]; Payne [5]; and Milchert, Hua and Makinen, [6].

The form of an idealised pressure pulse can be seen in Figure 5. The pulse starts with a relatively high pressure peak that moves from the keel line towards the chine of the hull. The pressure peak is characterised by a very short rise time (sometimes as little as 1 ms), and a fall time that is longer than the rise time. If the entry velocity is maintained there is a residual pressure after the first peak has passed. The magnitudes of the peak and residual pressures and the time domain characteristics of the pulse vary depending on type of vessel, velocity, seastate and geometry.

(a) As function of time

(b) Travelling across the hull

Figure 5. Idealised pressure pulse shape

x is wetted area by von Karman
 x' is modified wetted area by Wagner

Figure 6. Drop test wedge section

The classical approach taken by von Karman and Wagner is based on a falling 2-dimensional wedge having a predefined impact velocity and deadrise angle as shown in Figure 6. The pressure calculated by von Karman (eqn 1) is a mean pressure of the wetted area of the wedge, and is related to Bernoulli's equation for dynamic pressure in an incompressible fluid. (ρ is density of water, β is

deadrise angle). von Karman multiplies this equation with a constant, K (eqn 2), which is a function of deadrise angle and an assumption of added mass by the water.

$$P_{\max} = \frac{1}{2} \rho \cdot K \cdot v^2 \quad (1) \quad K = \pi \cdot \cot(\beta) \quad (2)$$

A modification of von Karman's work was made by Payne, [5], who considered a falling 2-D wedge impacting on water with spray root. Comparisons were made to Chuang's experimental data [4]. Payne suggested that most of the previous modifications made to von Karman's theory were inappropriate, including Wagner's theory of piled up water, and proposed the modifications shown in eqns 3 and 4. Figure 7 shows the mean pressures predicted by eqn 4 for typical deadrise angles and entry velocities. The pressures become very high at low deadrise angles and high velocities. For comparison, the design pressure from the DNV HSLC code [7] for the panel studied in this paper is only 65kPa.

$$K_{\text{mean}} = \frac{\pi \left(1 - \frac{\beta}{\pi}\right)}{\tan \beta} \quad (3) \quad P_{\text{mean}} = \frac{1}{2} \rho \cdot K_{\text{mean}} \cdot v^2 = \frac{1}{2} \rho \frac{\pi \left(1 - \frac{\beta}{\pi}\right)}{\tan \beta} \cdot v^2 \quad (4)$$

Figure 7. Mean pressure according to Payne [5]

Wagner's approach has been utilised as the basis of methods for predicting the maximum pressures by many researchers, including Stavovy and Chuang [4] and Faltinsen and Zhao [8]. In this work Stavovy and Chuang's approach is used, which considers a vertical impact velocity and a horizontal vessel velocity, with only the vertical velocity contributing to the slamming pressure. Bottom hull pressures are divided into two parts; maximum impact pressure, P_i (eqn 5) and planing pressure P_p (eqn 6). The model was validated by Stavovy and Chuang for drop tests at 0.3-3 m/s down to 1 degree deadrise with good correlation. k_1 is found from curve fitting to experimental data according to eqn 7. Figure 8 shows the resulting pressure curves, highlighting the reduction in pressures at very low deadrise angles due to air entrapment.

$$P_i = k_1 \cdot \rho \cdot V_n^2 \quad [psi] \quad (5) \quad P_p = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \rho \cdot V_t^2 \left(\frac{1}{144}\right) \quad [psi] \quad (6)$$

Where ρ is in slugs ($\text{lb}\cdot\text{sec}^2/\text{ft}^4$), V_n is fps (ft/sec) and P_i in psi (lb/in^2).

$$\begin{aligned} 0 \leq \beta \leq 2.2 \text{ deg:} & \quad k_1 = \frac{0.37 \cdot \beta}{2.2} + 0.5 \\ 2.2 \leq \beta \leq 11 \text{ deg:} & \quad k_1 = 4.748742 - 1.3450284 \cdot \beta + 0.1576516 \cdot \beta^2 - 0.0092976 \cdot \beta \\ & \quad + 0.0002735 \cdot \beta^4 - 0.0000031986 \cdot \beta^5 \\ 11 \leq \beta \leq 20 \text{ deg:} & \quad k_1 = 2.1820894 - 0.9451815 \cdot \beta + 0.2037541 \cdot \beta^2 - 0.0233896 \cdot \beta \\ & \quad + 0.0013578 \cdot \beta^4 - 0.00003132 \cdot \beta^5 \\ 20 \leq \beta \text{ deg (modified Wagner):} & \quad k_1 = \left[1 + \frac{2.4674}{\beta^2}\right] \frac{0.76856471}{\beta} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Figure 8. Peak pressure according to Stavovy and Chuang [4]

In addition to the pressure magnitudes it is also necessary to define the time domain shape of the pressure pulse. In previous work by Battley and Svensson [9] a simplified pressure pulse shape was used for transient dynamic FEA modelling. The pressure pulse was based on rise time, fall time, peak- and mean-pressure, as shown in Figure 9. To more accurately represent the pressure pulses observed in experimental data a more sophisticated form of the pressure pulse was developed, using pressure rise (eqn 8) and fall equations (eqn 9), a rise and fall pressure ratio, and peak and residual pressures. Different ratios of rise and fall times alter the form of the curve as shown in Figure 10.

Figure 9. Simplified pressure pulse from [9]

Figure 10. Modified pressure pulse

$$P_{rise} = r1 \cdot Pp \cdot \left(\frac{2t}{tr}\right)^a \quad (8)$$

$$P_{fall} = (Pp - Pr) \cdot e^{b(t-tr)} + Pr \quad (9)$$

Setting $P_{rise} = r1 \cdot Pp$ at $t = tr/2$ and $P_{fall} = r2 \cdot Pr$ at $t = (t+tr)$ gives:

$$a = \frac{\ln(r1)}{\ln(2)} \quad \text{and} \quad b = -\frac{1}{tf} \ln\left(\frac{Pr(r2-1)}{(Pp-Pr)}\right)$$

The pressure prediction model is used to generate a series of time-history curves representing the progression of the pressure pulse across the panel for transient finite element modelling. Input parameters are the velocity profile during the slamming event, specimen geometry, rise and fall time of pressure pulse (generally from experimental data), deceleration distance, time steps, and rise and fall ratio. A geometry function is used to represent the curved panel, velocity and deadrise angle are calculated across the panel, and then a pressure distribution generated for each row of elements. The maximum pressure is calculated from eqn 5, while the residual pressure is based on 0.6 times the mean pressure from eqn 4. Eqns 8 and 9 define the pulse shape. The output is a series of time-pressure histories in the FEA input text file format.

TRANSIENT DYNAMIC FINITE ELEMENT MODELLING

Modal transient finite element analysis was used to model slamming events for a composite sandwich panel using a commercial code (EMRC NISA V10.5). The specimen is a singly curved rectangular panel, 0.5m wide x 1.0m long, with a radius of curvature of 650mm. Wet layup 3.2mm thick skin laminates are glass/epoxy, with 2 layers of 1135g/mm² triaxial plies, covering angles of 0, 30, 60, 90, 120 150°, and an outer layer of 0/90° cloth of weight 350g/mm². The 25 mm thick foam core is 80 kg/m³ HEREX C70.75L. Material properties are given in Table 1. The basic modelling approach is described further in [9]. Temporally and spatially varying pressures were defined as described in the previous section. The specimen and surrounding support structures (Figures 11 and 12) were modelling using eight node quadratic shell element (NKTP32 for the sandwich panel, NKTP20 for the plywood support frames). Rigid links were used to represent aluminium support beams.

Figure 11. FEA mesh

Figure 12. Resultant displacement

The curved geometry of the specimen means that the deadrise angle changes across the panel, and hence for a constant entry velocity the peak and mean pressures vary across the panel. Since in the SSTS based experiments the velocity was not constant during the slamming event, the predicted pressure pulse was based on the measured velocity profile from the tests. An input file for the FEA code was then generated for the transient dynamic analysis. Figure 13 shows a typical set of pressure pulse curves for a slam test, in this case for an entry velocity of 4.5 m/s, which drops to a minimum of 2.5 m/s during the slamming event. Note how the pressure decreases as the pulse travels across the panel due to both the increasing deadrise and the reduction in velocity

Table 1 Material properties.

Property (MPa)	Faces	Core	Plywood Frame
E_x (MPa)	11500	81 comp., 63 tens.	12400
G_{xy} (MPa)	4420	28	6520
$\sigma_{\text{tension max}}$ (MPa)	183	1.9	
$\sigma_{\text{compr. Max}}$ (MPa)	207	1.3	
τ_{max} (MPa)		25	
ν_{xy}	0.3		0.1
ρ (kg/m ³)	1550	80	520

Figure 13. Simulated pressure pulse vs time at respective elements across the panel

SERVO-HYDRAULIC SLAM TESTING SYSTEM

Previous experimental measurements of slamming events have been performed by using "drop tests", where a specimen is dropped from a defined height onto the water surface, by using scale models in towing tanks, and on actual vessels. Many drop tests have used rigid models to investigate the resulting pressure distributions. Some of the classical early work in this field was undertaken by Chuang [10], who performed experiments on slamming of wedge-shaped bodies. More recent work includes that of Wraith [11], using rigid V-shaped, single and double curved specimens.

Only a limited number of drop tests using non-rigid panels have been performed. Hayman et al. [12, 13], used both aluminium and GRP sandwich specimens of 2x1.5m. Pressure, acceleration and strains were measured. At 30 deg. and 7m drop height pressures of 1.5-2 bar were measured, with 5 deg. and 2m drop height pressures of 12-14 bar were measured. Katsaounis and Samuelides [14] have performed drop tests, primarily related to wetdeck slamming [14]. These were from heights of 0.5 to 2.5m, for various panel sizes up to 2x1.7m and included both aluminum and CFRP sandwich panels. Peak pressures of up to 4-5 bar were measured. Other drop tests include those by Faltinsen [15] who undertook drop tests from 1-2 m on a 0.5x1.0m flat plate, and measured peak pressures of 80 bar.

The main drawback of drop tests is that there is no control of the specimen motion once it hits the water. The entry velocity is controlled by the drop height, and the mass of the specimen can be changed, influencing the rate of retardation once the specimen enters the water. In reality the velocity profile during a slamming event depends on the overall behaviour of the vessel and the position of the panel. Initially the entry velocity of the hull may be relatively constant, so a panel near to the keel will experience a constant magnitude pressure pulse. As more of the hull is immersed the vertical velocity of the vessel reduces, meaning that a panel near to the dynamic waterline may experience pressure loads that decrease as the pulse traverses the panel.

While it is possible to make measurements of panel response on real vessels, it is difficult to reproduce particular conditions in real vessel testing due to the large number of variables present. The possible instrumentation is also usually limited by access to the hull skin, and by the need to destructively modify the panels for some measurements such as pressure and core strains.

A Servo-hydraulic Slam testing System (SSTS) has been developed at Industrial Research Limited to enable controlled slamming tests to be performed. The system subjects full size marine panels to impact with a water surface to simulate slam loading. A servo-hydraulic system provides control over the panel motion during the water impact. This enables measured motions from real vessels to be reproduced in a laboratory with comprehensive instrumentation. The system uses a 3.5m diameter tank with a water depth of 1.5m as shown in Figures 14 and 15. The specimen is guided by a linear track system, with vertical panels on three sides of the specimen to constrain the water flow. To date the specimens used have been 0.5 wide by 1.0 long, although there is no particular limitation on the panel size, apart from the force capacity of the ram. Parameters measured include pressure, displacement, velocity, accelerations and ram force. Resistance strain gauges are used on the skin of the sandwich panels and within the foam core.

Design of the servo-hydraulic system to achieve the required velocities of up to 10m/s with adequate control has been a significant challenge. A custom ram/accumulator /manifold/servo-valve installation was designed to maximise the flow rate and hence ram velocity. The system has proven to be capable

of more than 10m/s, however the level of control provided by a conventional digital PID controller has not been as good as desired. The main difficulty has been achieving a feedback control system with adequate stability to maintain constant velocity prior to the impact, and then to be able to respond to the change in load at impact. The hydraulics and control system have been modified during the development of the system. Future revisions to the system will increase the ram's force capacity, increase the natural frequency of the mechanical/hydraulic system, and provide a much higher level of feedback control than with the current displacement feedback PID controller.

Figure 14. Overall view of SSTS

Figure 15. Panel specimen in SSTS

CORRELATION BETWEEN EXPERIMENTS AND PREDICTIONS

Figure 16 shows the portion of a typical impact event in the servo-hydraulic slamming system that corresponds to the time span of the FE analysis. The “piled up” water is clearly visible in Figure 16 (a) and (d). Figure 17 shows the load, velocity and displacement traces for a typical slamming event. The phases include an initial acceleration from rest, a constant velocity region prior to impact, a drop in velocity after impact due to control system limitations, then an increase before the system is halted by a proximity switch which closes the servo valve.

Figure 16. Images from typical slamming test

Figures 18 to 21 present results for a slamming impact test with an initial impact velocity of 4.5m/s. Note that this is a different event that those shown in Figures 16 and 17. Figure 18 shows the simulated pressure pulse vs. the corresponding experimental results. There is very good correlation with the peak pressure predicted by eqn 5. Figure 19 shows the experimental ram force and the corresponding force from the FEA simulation. Only the first 20-30 ms are of relevance since the post

impact increase in load represents motion of the fully immersed panel that is not modelled in the simulation. There is reasonably good correlation in the magnitudes and frequency of the load oscillations. As shown in Figure 20, the magnitudes of the normal accelerations at the centre of the panel are similar; however the first small dip of the experimental result was unexpected. It is possible that the inertia of the panel itself may have created a negative acceleration at the centre of the panel before the pressure pulse reached that position. Figure 21 shows the surface strains at the centre of the panel. The measured results for these do not correlate very well with the experimental data, the measured strains being approximately one third of those predicted. This is unexpected since the pressure magnitude, loads and accelerations measured were approximately the same for the first phase of the loading and higher during the second phase of the impact event so one would expect the strains to follow the same pattern. The strains also show an initial negative dip, similar to the one seen in the acceleration. This dip was present for all of the tests performed to date. Because the panel is stationary in the FEA modelling the simulated behaviour does not include any rigid body motion related inertial affects, which may be a contributing factor to the discrepancies in acceleration and strains.

Figure 17. Typical impact event with open-loop control

Figure 18. Simulated pressure pulse vs. experimental for initial impact velocity of 4.5m/s

Figure 19. Simulated load vs. experimental data for initial impact velocity of 4.5m/s

Figure 21. Simulated strains vs. experimental data for initial impact velocity of 4.5m/s

Figures 22 and 23 summarise the pressure and load results for entry velocities ranging from 2.2 to 4.5 m/s. There is a very good correlation in the pressure, and reasonable correlation in the load. The plateau at the higher load level is believed to be due to limitations in the hydraulic system's force capability. The good correlation in the pressure magnitudes implies that the panel deformation does not significantly change the pressure pulse.

Figure 22. Pressure vs entry velocity

Figure 23. Load vs entry velocity

CONCLUSIONS

The pressure simulation method proposed appears to accurately represent the pressures observed in slamming tests. The method enables transient dynamic finite element modelling to be used to simulate composite panel responses to a slamming load. Measured loads and panel accelerations correlate reasonably well with those predicted by the modelling, however the skin strains measured on the panel are lower than those predicted. This may be because the FEA modelling does not include any rigid body motion related inertial effects. The present configuration of the servo-hydraulic slam testing system is limited in its ability to maintain a constant velocity throughout the slamming event, and needs to have greater force capacity. Both of these are currently being addressed. Future work will further investigate correlation between modelling and experimental responses, and use the SSTS to assist with development and verification of coupled fluid-structure modelling approaches.

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